

GENOMED4ALL

Genomics for Next Generation Healthcare

D8.3

GENOMED4ALL standardization final report

Revision v1

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Abstract

Data standardization involves transforming data into a consistent common format to enable, among others, data interoperability. Representation of genomic information is highly varied and complex. Several well-known formats and tools have been developed to store and exchange such data. Despite this, there remains a high level of heterogeneity involving the use of different terminologies, conventions, and assumptions making genomic data integration challenging. Precise actual representation of genomic information is important for the application of artificial intelligence in a clinical context. In this report we review the current state of the art and the

interoperability needs of the different scenarios of Genomed4all use cases. In addition, we outline the standardization requirements to a) include new data to keep training the AI models and b) input individual patient data to obtain clinical predictions.

Keywords

Genomic standardization, next generation sequencing (NGS), large-scale genomics, file formats, interoperability

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*** Deliverable types:****R:** document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).**DEM:** demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.**DEC:** websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.**OTHER:** software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

ABRF	Association of Biomolecular Resource Facilities
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BAM	Binary Alignment Map
BED	Browser Extensible Data
CNA	Copy Number Alteration
COSMIC	Catalogue of Somatic Mutations in Cancer
EGA	European Genome-phenome Archive
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
FDA	Food and Drug Administration
FGED	Functional Genomics Data society
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GIAB	Genome in a Bottle project
GWAS	Genome Wide Association Studies
HbS	Hemoglobin S (abnormal)
HDs	Hematological Diseases
HGNC	HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee
IT	Information Technology
MAQC	MicroArray Quality Control Project
MDS	Myelodysplastic Syndromes
MIAME	Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment
MIGS-MIMS	Minimum Information about a Metagenomic Sequence
MINSEQE	Minimum information about a high-throughput sequencing experiment
MM	Multiple Myeloma
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
NIST	National Institute of Standards and Technology
SAM	Sequence Alignment Map
SCD	Sickle Cell Disease
SNP	Single Nucleotide Polymorphism
SNV	Single Nucleotide Variant
ULP-WGS	Ultra-low pass whole-genome sequencing
VCF	Variant Call Format

WES	Whole Exome Sequencing
WGS	Whole Genome Sequencing

1 Executive summary

The decreasing cost of genomic sequencing and the consequent increased use in clinical settings will favor the generation of sequencing data from millions of humans. If those datasets were shared, they would represent an invaluable resource for the study of the genetic basis of diseases. The representation of genomic information is varied and complex and it poses a great challenge for data integration and bioinformatic analysis. Defining genotype representation requires a careful conceptual consensus and semantic precision for interoperability. The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH), formed in 2013, is one of the most relevant bodies dedicated to advancing human health through genomic data. To address the challenge of aligning genomic data, the GA4GH works towards the design of genomic knowledge standards, as the VCF (Variant Call Format).

Genomed4all is focused on three different hematological disorders and aims to build a platform for the development and validation of artificial intelligence (AI) models to improve patient's outcomes through precision medicine. The genomic profiling of patients is essential to address the main challenges in the management of the diseases considered by the use cases. Each research group has internally developed specific bioinformatic pipelines to process the genomic data for each use case. A well-defined workflow was followed to obtain high-quality and reproducible results. Those pre-processing pipelines generated the files that are ingested by the AI models. This report reviews the current state of the art and focuses on the interoperability needs of the different Genomed4all scenarios presenting the standardization requirements to a) include new data to keep training the AI models and b) input individual patient data to obtain clinical predictions. The report discusses the challenges and limitations regarding genomic standardization and general recommendations.

2 State of the Art

Next-generation sequencing (NGS) has revolutionized the analysis of the human genome, and the gradual cost reduction is increasing its use in clinical genomics. Besides, the possibility of reusing those datasets generated in healthcare highly contributes to the advancement of research in medicine. Integrating data from various sources to create larger datasets is key to expanding the knowledge of a given topic or disease. However, the integration of complex and multidimensional datasets is one of the great challenges of modern bioinformatics. In this regard, and with the perspective of delivering the benefits from genomic science to the population, researchers and clinicians should come together and agree on common methods and standards for collecting, storing, analyzing and sharing health genomics.

One major obstacle in data integration lies in the heterogeneity of data formats across the different healthcare domains. Integrating such data requires careful consideration of biological variations to ensure that observed patterns are genuine and not artifacts of the integration process, for example. Standardized procedures, dictionaries, data formats, and comprehensive quality management considerations are the cornerstones of data integration.

NGS depends on several file types to store data at various stages of the analysis pipeline. The sequencing of a sample (DNA or RNA) generates many short (or long depending on the technology) reads deposited in a file with associated quality scores (FASTQ). This format is the starting point for most genomic analyses and has become a cornerstone of many genomic analysis pipelines, as the quality scores are critical for the assessment of the reliability of the sequence data. Then, those reads are aligned to a reference genome or sequence and the results are deposited in an alignment file (BAM/SAM). BAM (the binary version of SAM) is a compact and efficient format for storing substantial amounts of alignment data, while SAM is a human-readable format. There are several types of quantitative data that can be generated after processing BAM and SAM files, including quality scores, coverage, structural variations, epigenetic analysis, and genomic variants. Regarding the latter, the VCF is widely used for storing and sharing information about genomic variants, such as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNP) and insertions/deletions. Finally, the variant file is further analyzed to determine which findings are clinically relevant (see Figure 1). VCF files provide a standardized way of describing and comparing genomic variants across different samples, and in fact it is the most common format in clinical practice. The specifications for variant files were initially developed to be flexible regarding content representation but at the same time provide a level of consistency with respect to data elements (more details about VCF and its standardization can be found in D8.1). This flexibility allows variation about how sequence findings are described, and this depends, in part, on the conventions used. On the other hand, this poses a problem because these differences can compromise the capability to compare sequence findings and identify clinically relevant variants. It is important to highlight that those specifications were mainly developed to support a diverse variety of research applications rather than clinical practice.

Many initiatives promoted and aimed at genomic data standardization at different levels [Adapted from Brancato, V. et al. (2024)] [1]:

a) metadata standards

MIGS-MIMS (Minimum Information about a Metagenomic Sequence) is a standard developed and maintained by the Genomic Standards Consortium for describing contextual information about the sampling and sequencing of any genomic sequence. It is adopted by diverse laboratories using different sequencing technologies and it consists of a checklist (with required, recommended and optional metadata) to standardize the description of a genomic sequence (metadata) [2]. Related initiatives are MIAME (Minimum Information About a Microarray Experiment) [3] and [MINSEQE](#) (Minimum information about a high-throughput sequencing experiment) proposed by the Functional Genomics Data Society (FGED) aimed at defining a minimum set of metadata and facilitating standardization, reproducibility of the experiments and data sharing.

b) data analysis and quality metrics projects and tools

MicroArray Quality Control Project ([MAQC](#)), with the support of the FDA, focuses on the necessity of comparability between results obtained from different platforms and the development of standards and quality guidelines for their reliable use in clinical practice. The MAQC also works towards the development of advanced data analysis techniques for microarrays

c) file formats

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health ([GA4GH](#)) is an international organization contributing to developing guidelines and tools to facilitate the FAIRness of genomic data and unlock the great potential of genomics in medicine. Among the main standards is the already mentioned VCF and also Beacon for data discoverability.

d) data integration

Other organizations, such as the US ([NIST](#)), work towards the standardization of sample preparation through a number of projects. Besides, Genome in a Bottle ([GIAB](#)) consortium focused on adapting established procedures for whole-genome sequencing to the clinical setting. The Association of Biomolecular Resource Facilities ([ABRF](#)) works comparing performance of different NGS sequencing platforms to optimize methods and strategies as well as the development of standardized guidelines.

The combined analysis of genomic data with clinically relevant data from electronic health records using artificial intelligence algorithms could dramatically improve the diagnostic yield of genetic testing. Genomed4all aims to build a platform where clinicians and researchers can work together in the development and validation of AI models to improve the manner hematological diseases (HDs) are diagnosed and treated in the EU. For the application of such AI technologies in the real-world standardization is a critical step. In terms of genomic data, standards should be established to a) structure the input data to the AI model to ensure consistency across health systems, and b) set quality metrics to validate the data utilized in the models.

Figure 1. Typical Next Generation Sequencing workflow

3 Genomic data & analysis overview

Hematological diseases are disorders of the blood and blood-forming organs. In addition to blood cell cancers, HDs also include rare genetic disorders, anemia and sickle cell disease, among others. Most HDs have an inherited or acquired genetic background, being the cause of severe chronic health problems and life-threatening conditions. Genomed4all focuses on three different diseases: Myelodysplastic Syndromes (MDS), Sickle Cell Disease (SCD) and Multiple Myeloma (MM). In these diseases genomic profiling is important as it can improve disease classification, diagnosis or treatment stratification. The clinical aims mentioned in this section are summarized from D7.1 where extended information can be found.

Myelodysplastic syndromes

Myelodysplastic Syndromes are myeloid neoplasms characterized by clonal proliferation of hematopoietic stem cells, recurrent genetic abnormalities, myelodysplasia, ineffective hematopoiesis, peripheral-blood cytopenia, and a high risk of evolution to acute myeloid leukemia. MDS are mainly sporadic diseases affecting older people. Recurrently mutated driver genes include those involving RNA splicing, DNA methylation, histone modification, transcription regulation, DNA repair control, signaling, and the cohesin complex. Just six genes (SF3B1, TET2, SRSF2, ASXL1, DNMT3A, and RUNX1) are mutated in at least 10% of patients who have MDS, with a long list of additional genes that are mutated less frequently. At the onset of clinical disease, the median number of driver mutations is two or three per patient [4]. In GenoMed4All genomic profiling of patients is used to address key challenges in the management of the disease:

- ❑ **Aim 1:** identify elderly individuals at high risk of developing MDS.
11,000 healthy elderly subjects (aged >65y) from population-based studies with clinical information were sequenced by targeted mutation screening (NGS on 50 genes related to clonal hematopoiesis) to analyze somatic mutational features as type of mutation, presence of co-mutations or variant allele frequencies.
- ❑ **Aim 2:** improve “Omics”-based classification and prognosis of MDS
6,700 MDS patients with clinical features and information on targeted mutation screening (NGS including 60 genes related to MDS); 1,200 MDS patients with data on RNA-sequencing of hematopoietic progenitors; 900 MDS patients with whole exome/genome sequencing to analyze somatic mutational patterns and structural variants.
- ❑ **Aim 3:** improve “Omics”-based clinical decision making in MDS
1,500 MDS patients who received transplantation with clinical features and information on targeted mutation screening (NGS including 60 genes related to MDS) to analyze somatic mutational patterns and structural variants.

Sickle cell disease

Sickle-cell disease is a multisystem disease, associated with episodes of acute illness and progressive organ damage, and is one of the most common severe monogenic disorders worldwide. This disease includes all the different genotypes that cause the characteristic clinical syndrome, whereas sickle-cell anemia, the most common form of sickle-cell disease, refers

specifically to homozygosity for the β S allele (β hemoglobin sub-unit). Abnormal hemoglobin S (HbS) is caused by a mutation in the β -globin gene in which the 17th nucleotide is changed from thymine to adenine and the sixth amino acid in the β -globin chain becomes valine instead of glutamic acid. This substitution of a polar glutamate by a non-polar valine in an invariant region generates a protein that polymerizes under deoxygenated conditions sickling the patient's erythrocytes. Although SCD is caused by the exact same mutation in every patient, the disease is very unpredictable and has a very heterogeneous clinical phenotype. The main determinant of disease severity is the rate and extent of HbS polymerisation, which is exemplified by co-inheritance of genetic factors that modulate the intracellular HbS or fetal hemoglobin concentration [5]. In Genomed4all genomic profiling of patients is used to predict the outcome given the phenotype variability.

- **Aim 1:** classify SCD patients in different groups according to their genomic profile and assess correlation with inflammation related markers, point of sickling and phenotype. A GWAS analysis was performed in approximately 1,000 patients with SCD to identify SNPs associated with severity of the disease.

Multiple Myeloma

Multiple myeloma (MM) is a neoplastic plasma-cell disorder that accounts for approximately 13% of all hematologic cancers. It is characterized by clonal proliferation of malignant plasma cells in the bone marrow microenvironment, monoclonal protein in the blood or urine, and associated organ dysfunction. Myeloma arises from an asymptomatic premalignant proliferation of monoclonal plasma cells that are derived from post-germinal-center B cells. Multistep genetic and microenvironmental changes lead to the transformation of these cells into a malignant neoplasm. Chromosomal aberration is a hallmark of MM, in 30% of the cases, primary early chromosomal translocations occur at the immunoglobulin switch region resulting in the deregulation of two adjacent genes, MMSET in all cases and FGFR3 [6]. Besides, several copy number alterations have been described as prominent genomic alterations acquired during tumor progression in MM patients [7]. In Genomed4all genomic profiling of patients is used to predict the risk of early relapse for each patient.

- **Aim 1:** To provide a prognostic stratification of patients it is needed to integrate baseline genomic, clinical and imaging data to identify high-risk patients (as defined as patients relapsing within one year from the start of treatment, regardless from therapy employed). Genomic data were analyzed from a cohort of 253 MM patients. Plasma cells (CD138+) DNA from bone marrow aspiration was profiled using two molecular methods: SNP arrays for 171 patients and ultra-low pass whole-genome sequencing for 82 patients (ULP-WGS - average coverage of 0.5X).

Use Case 1 – MDS (Myelodysplastic syndromes), myeloid neoplasm		
Aim 1. MDS prevention based on genomic screening		
<i>Cohort: 11,000 healthy elderly subjects (>65yo)</i>		
Genomic data:	Result:	Conclusions:
Targeted mutation screening - NGS on 50 genes related to clonal hematopoiesis	Small Nucleotide Variants	Somatic mutational pattern
Aim 2: “Omics”-based classification and prognosis of MDS		
Genomic data	Result:	Conclusions:
Targeted mutation screening - NGS on 60 genes related to MDS / RNA sequencing of hematopoietic progenitors (1200 patients) / Whole exome/genome sequencing (900 patients)	Small Nucleotide Variants	Somatic mutational pattern
Aim 3: “Omics”-based clinical decision making in MDS		
Genomic data	Result:	Conclusions:
Targeted mutation screening - NGS on 60 genes related to MDS	Small Nucleotide Variants	Somatic mutational pattern
Use Case 2 – SCD (Sickle-cell disease), rare genetic hematological disorder		
Aim: Predict personal outcomes of SCD patients		
<i>Cohort: About 1,000 patients</i>		
Genomic data	Result:	Conclusions:
SNP array	GWAS /SNVs	Dosage of alternative allele
Use Case 3 – MM (Multiple myeloma), neoplasm		
Aim: Define risk of progression for each patient		
Genomic data <i>Cohort 1: 171 patients</i>	Result:	Conclusions:
SNP array	Copy number alterations (CNA)	Presence/absence of amplifications or deletions
Genomic data <i>Cohort: 82 patients</i>	Result:	Conclusions:
Ultra-low pass whole-genome sequencing (0.5X)	Copy number alterations (CNA)	Presence/absence of amplifications or deletions

Table 1. Summary genomic data available and analysis

4 Genomic data standardization

In GenoMed4All each use case addresses key unmet clinical needs in each of the above-mentioned hematological diseases, for which relevant samples have been collected and data analyzed (described in deliverable D5.2 and D5.4). Each research group has internally developed specific bioinformatic pipelines to process the genomic data for each use case. A well-defined workflow must be followed to obtain high-quality and reproducible results. Detailed bioinformatic pipelines are reported in deliverable D5.2. The resulting output files of the preprocessing pipelines will be the source data (input files) for the development of the AI models. In GenoMed4All file standardization is essential to:

- A) Allow potential new prospective or retrospective patient data to be included in the AI models to create an ever-learning model.
- B) To format the input individual patient data into the platform for AI prediction
- C) Contribute to data FAIRification (interoperability and reusability)
- D) Data sharing

In this section we report the key points for genomic standardization in each use case.

MYELODISPLASTIC SYNDROME

The MDS pipeline is tailored to a custom gene panel of about 50 genes (30 of them important for the classification of MDS). The genes included in the panel are:

ASXL1, ATRX, BCOR, BCORL1, BRAF, CBL, CBLB, CEBPA, DNMT3A, ETV6, EZH2, FBXW7, FLT3, GATA2, GNAS, GNB1, IDH1, IDH2, JAK2, KIT, KRAS, MPL, NF1, NOTCH1, NPM1, NRAS, PHF6, PIGA, PRPF40B, PTPN11, RAD2, RUNX1 (AML1), SF3B1, SMC1A, SMC3, SRSF2, STAG2, TET2, TP53, U2AF, UTX (KDM6A), WT1, ZRSR2, CSF3R, SETBP1, CALR, PPM1D

The output file and its standardization

The output file is a CSV file containing the following information for each patient (row) and for each of the MDS target gene (column):

- (i) the presence or absence of specific mutation (coded as one – presence or zero - absence)
- (ii) the number of different detected variants
- (iii) the associated variants allele frequency (VAF), calculated as the number of reads supporting the variant divided by the total of sequenced reads.

The csv file contains columns with the following information:

- **Patient ID**
- *Gene A result*
- *Gene A n.mutations*
- *Gene A load*
- *Gene B result*
- *Gene B n.mutations*
- *Gene B load*

■ ...

The 'result' columns contain binary information:

- If result = 0: the gene was sequenced but no mutation was found
- If result = 1: the gene was sequenced, and one or more mutations were found
- If the gene was not sequenced there are not code, the cell is empty

The 'n.mutations' columns collects the number of mutations in that specific gene

The 'load' shows the variant allele fraction (% of mutation). In case of more than one mutation detected in the same gene it will appear different percentages, corresponding with the VAF of each specific mutation, separated with a separator. In other words, if two mutations are present in the same gene, two values will be indicated for each mutation respectively.

MDS							
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	Patient ID	GEN_A result	GEN_A n. mutations	GEN_A load	GEN_B result	GEN_B n. mutations	GEN_B load
2	indv_001	1	1	31.91	NA	NA	NA
3	indv_002	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
4	indv_003	NA	NA	NA	0	0	NA
5	indv_004	NA	NA	NA	0	0	NA
6	indv_005	0	0	NA	0	0	NA
7	indv_006	0	0	NA	NA	NA	NA
8	indv_007	1	1	3.16	0	0	NA
9	indv_008	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA	NA
10	indv_009	0	0	NA	0	0	NA
11	indv_010	0	0	NA	0	0	NA

1. Patient ID
2. Gene names
3. Gene mutation
4. Number of mutations
5. VAF

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Figure 2. Example MDS output csv file

To accept new patient data in MDS use case:

For the preprocessing pipeline:

- The formats allowed are FASTQ or BAM files. VCFs are not supported.
- As reference genome the pipeline requires hg38
- The AI model supports only the genes included in the targeted panel, but in case less genes (from the list) are sequenced, the ones missing can appear as incomplete information.
- The name of the genes should be standardized following HGNC nomenclature.

For AI model:

- As direct input for the AI model, the output csv file is required as it is previously described.

Pipeline: key considerations for standardization

- A description of the pipeline and the commands can be found in deliverable 5.2 and 5.4.

- To annotate the functional consequences of genetic variations the pipeline considered both public databases as well as an “in-house” database. The “in-house” database was created based on previous clinical results and experience from researchers and clinicians within the consortium; it is a whitelist of variants with known oncogenic potential. The internal whitelist is currently not publicly available.
 - Only variants with coverage > 500x and VAF > 1% were analyzed.
 - Allele frequencies were depicted using 1000Genomes project, the Exome Sequencing Project, Exome Aggregation Consortium and GnomAD databases.
 - To identify the oncogenic potential of the variants it was used the Catalogue of Somatic Mutations in Cancer (COSMIC) v91 in at least 10 myeloid neoplasms (<https://cancer.sanger.ac.uk/cosmic>)
 - The remaining variants were considered as possible somatic mutations, and their pathogenic value was evaluated to differentiate known and putative pathogenic mutations from variants of unclear significance by using a multi-step algorithm:
 - All variants (missense, in-frame insertions/deletions, frameshift, nonsense and splice site) were considered pathogenic if they were previously reported in COSMIC database at least in two hematological samples.
 - Loss of function mutations (nonsense, frameshift and splice site) were considered pathogenic.
 - Missense variants and in-frame insertions/deletions not fulfilling these criteria were individually assessed based on the available data from COSMIC (the tissues they were found in, whether any other COSMIC variants were reported affecting the same amino-acid positions)
 - Non-synonymous variants not fulfilling these criteria were then classified on the basis of their functional interpretation using in silico prediction effect. The algorithms used were SIFT 1.03, FATHMM, PolyPhen 2.0 and MutationTaster 1.0. Extensive details about the workflow can be found in D5.2 and D5.4. Variants must be predicted as damaging at the amino acid level by all algorithms.
- The MDS pipeline is available in CINECA Galileo 100 (G100) servers to automatically process other MDS patients' raw data if available from other consortium partners or external partners that request to be part of the consortium.

SICKLE CELL DISEASE

The SCD pipeline uses GWAS to identify disease-associated SNPs across the whole genome using a commercial SNP array.

The output file and its standardization:

The output file is a CSV file containing the following information.

Column 1: sample_id - Unique identifier for each individual sample.

Columns 2 (and so on): SNP Columns (e.g., rs1000010, rs1000020, ...) - Each column represents a specific SNP, labeled by its rsID. The values in these columns indicate the dosage of the alternate allele for that SNP in the respective sample.

Data Explanation:

Dosage values are continuous values ranging from 0 to 2.

- 0 indicates no copies of the alternate allele (homozygous reference).
- 1 indicates one copy of the alternate allele (heterozygous).
- 2 indicates two copies of the alternate allele (homozygous alternate).
- Intermediate values (e.g., 0.5, 1.3) indicate probabilities based on imputation.

SDC						
	A	B	C	D	E	F
1	sample_id	rs1000010	rs1000020	rs1000030	rs1000040	rs1000050
2	indiv_001	1.2	0.8	1.9	0.5	1.1
3	indiv_002	0.9		1 1.7	1.2	1
4	indiv_003	1.5	0.7	1.8		1 1.3
5	indiv_004	0.8	1.2	0.9	1.1	1.4
6	indiv_005	1.1	1.3		1 0.9	1.2
7	indiv_006	1.3	0.9	1.1		1 1.5
8	indiv_007		1 1.5	0.8	1.3	0.9
9	indiv_008	1.4	0.6	1.3	0.7	1
10	indiv_009	0.7	1.1	1.5	1.2	1.3
11	indiv_010	1.2		1 1.4	1.1	1.1

1. Sample ID
2. SNPs (labeled as rsID)
3. Dosage values for each SNP

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Figure 3. Example SDC output file

To accept new patient data in SDC use case:

For the preprocessing pipeline:

- The input file format for the pipeline can be PLINK or GEN. Since VCF can be easily transformed into PLINK, VCF could be another potential input format for the pipeline.
- The imputation panel could be TopMed or 1000Genomes project.
- The input data can be generated using WGS technologies but not WES.

For AI model:

- As direct input for the AI model, the output csv file is required as previously described.

Pipeline: key considerations for standardization

- A description of the pipeline can be found in deliverable 5.2.
- Genomic variants are called by rsIDs, not by coordinates. (Consider that not all existing variants have a stablished rsID).

MULTIPLE MYELOMA

The MM pipeline analyzes CNAs from data obtained by a SNP array technology or WGS (ultralow pass) from samples of newly diagnosed MM patients.

The output file and its standardization

The output file is a CSV containing the following information for each patient (row):

- ❑ Method: Refers to the sequencing technology. It can be an SNP array or any WGS technology.
 - Value =1: SNP array
 - Value =2: WGS (Ultralow pass)
- ❑ Amplifications: the amplification columns (named ‘amp’) in the csv represent the presence or absence of amplification in each arm of every chromosome. Each ‘amp’ column represents one of the arms (p or q) of every chromosome (amp_1p; amp_1q...).
 - Value=0: Absence of amplification
 - Value=1: Presence of amplification
- ❑ Deletions: the deletion columns (named ‘del’) in csv represent the presence or absence of deletions in each the arms (p or q) of every chromosome. Each column represents one of the arms of each chromosome (del_1p; del_1q...).
 - Value=0: Absence of deletion
 - Value=1: Presence of deletion

MM								
	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	
1	id	Method	amp_1p	amp_1q	...	del_1p	del_1q	...
2	indv_001	1	0	0		1	0	
3	indv_002	1	0	1		0	0	
4	indv_003	1	0	0		0	0	
5	indv_004	1	0	0		0	0	
6	indv_005	1	0	1		0	0	
7	indv_006	1	0	0		0	0	
8	indv_007	1	0	0		0	0	
9	indv_008	1	0	0		0	0	
10	indv_009	1	0	0		0	0	
11								

1. Patient ID
 2. Sequencing technology
 3. Amplifications (arm p or q)
 4. Deletions (arm p or q)

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Figure 3. Example MM output file

To accept new patient data in MM pipeline:

For the preprocessing pipeline:

- The input file format for the pipeline can be FASTQ, BAM or intermediate BED files.
- The input data can be generated using WGS technologies but not WES.
- As reference genome the pipeline supports hg19 (the one used in this Genomed4all use case) and hg38.

For AI model:

- As direct input for the AI model, the output csv file is required as previously described.

Pipeline: key consideration standardization

- A description of the pipeline can be found in deliverable 5.2. The pipeline is available in Github: https://github.com/bioinformatic-seragnoli/GenoMed_MM
- The SNP array pipeline is no longer maintained (legacy). Only WGS is actually supported by the bioinformatic pipeline.
- The given copy number value per arm is estimated by a weighted average of the copy number values of the segments, using their length as the weight, and only changes affecting 50% of the cells were called (amplifications ≥ 2.50 and deletions ≤ 1.50).
- The MM pipeline is available in CINECA Galileo 100 (G100) servers to automatically process other patients' raw data if available from other consortium partners or external partners that request to be part of the consortium.

Use case	MDS	SDC	MM
Input formats supported	FASTQ BAM	PLINK GEN (VCF)	FASTQ BAM BED
Reference genome	hg38		hg38/ hg19
Imputation panel		TopMed / 1000 Genomes phase 3 (2014 release)	
Other considerations	Only genes in targeted panel	WGS but not WES	WGS but not WES

Figure 4. File formats summary

5 Standardization limitations

Genomic data standardization is intended to improve consistency, interoperability, and analysis of large-scale genomic information, with special importance for the translation of NGS into clinical practice. However, in general terms, the adoption of reference standards for NGS in this field has been slow. The bioinformatic pipelines for the analysis of NGS are often complex and its standardization remains challenging; several limitations hinder the full realization of the benefits. Some limitations root on the inherent complexity of genomics, the evolving nature of technologies or, in many cases, the diverse needs of the projects.

In Genomed4all the three different use cases addressed different clinical challenges with diverse needs in terms of genomic data. MDS use case aim to identify mutation and indels starting from NGS of a gene panel, while SCD and MM use cases start from a SNP array (or also WGS in MM) performed GWAS and CNA analysis, respectively. The differences in the input file formats supported by the pipelines (FASTQ, BAM, BED, PLINK, GEN) are partially due to the specific needs of the use case. MDS and MM use cases, can accept FASTQ and BAM, while SDS can accept PLINK and GEN.

One general limitation of standardization methodologies is the **lack of consensus on oncogenic variant classification**. Differences in classification practices can lead to discrepancies in how variants are reported across different studies. In Genomed4all, for example, the MDS pipeline analyzes somatic mutations using a targeted gene panel, to annotate the pathogenicity of the genetic variation uses both public databases as well as an ‘in house’ registry. While the ‘in house’ database of mutations supposes a valuable resource based on their real-world experience about the disease, it can also limit the reproducibility and interpretability for users outside the project.

Another detected limitation is the **adaptation to new sequencing technologies** and the progressive discarding of more obsolete workflows. As sequencing technologies evolve, so must the analysis, formats and other interoperability standards. This fact has two sides, first it can suppose a delay in the integration of the new technologies (and associated standards) into established workflows, and at the same time, but on the opposite side, it can suppose the gradual and discontinued maintenance of outdated packages and software. For example, in Genomed4all, the MM pipeline that analyzes CNA, integrates two different technologies (SNP array and WGS) in the analysis workflow. Although the SNP array is a technology still in use, the cost reduction of WGS and its accelerated adoption in clinical settings is replacing the former one. Actually, the SNP array technology is being deprecated by the institution leading the SDC use case (and being replaced by NGS), which highlights the problem of maintaining tools for unused and evolving technologies. The real-world situation is that both technologies co-exist, being of special importance the consideration of SNP arrays when combining retrospective data.

It is important to mention the inability to perform genotype imputation using the TOPMed reference panel. Although TOPMed offers high-quality imputation, its use requires data transfer to servers hosted by the University of Michigan in the United States. Due to data protection regulations within

Europe and the absence of a signed data processing agreement with the University of Michigan, it was not possible to transfer personal GWAS data for imputation. Although synthetic could be used for this purpose, the project's patient data could not be processed in this way due to privacy constraints. This highlights a broader challenge in cross-border genomic research, where regulatory constraints can limit access to state-of-the-art resources.

An additional aspect to consider for genomic standardization is nomenclature. In the SDC scenario the output of the pipeline includes rsIDs, instead of genomic coordinates, as reference. An intrinsic drawback of using rsIDs to identify SNPs is the fact that not all variants are represented by those unique IDs. Also, in this regard it is important to mention that rsID does not specify the nucleotide change, which can be important in some contexts. The same rsID with a different nucleotide change can have a different biological meaning.

The limitations mentioned illustrate how genomic standardization is a complex challenge that still needs ongoing efforts to develop and implement flexible and practical solutions. Collaboration among researchers, clinicians, IT teams & experts and standardization entities is essential to find optimal conventions. Training and education on the importance of using standards appears as the first pathway to engage the community in this endeavor.

6 Conclusions

Recommendations and next steps

GenoMed4All presented three different scenarios with different genomic standardization needs. Beyond the hurdles that standardization still needs to overcome, there are some crucial cornerstones that need to be fulfilled for successful data integration and sharing. In this section we are going to summarize key points for each use case, general recommendations and best practices that are aimed at facilitating data standardization.

1. Description of accepted input file formats for bioinformatic pre-processing:

For data integration purposes it is important to pinpoint which are the possible external data entry points at the bioinformatic pipeline, and the specific format required. In Genomed4all, the genomic pipelines developed can process external data when the data is integrated following some specific standards previously described (FASTQ, BAM, BED, PLINK; GEN). The input formats are listed in Figure 2. In the MDS use case the integration of new data is preferred as FASTQ file or BAM file. Alternatively, it can incorporate the final CSV file which includes the following information: presence/absence of mutations, number of mutations and VAF. In the SDC use case external data can be integrated as PLINK or GEN. In the MM use case, new data can be integrated as FASTQ, BAM or BED files. It is important to mention that the SDC and MM pipelines work with short reads that can be generated by different WGS technologies, but they do not accept WES.

2. Specify the reference genome:

An important point for reproducibility is always to mention the genome assembly.

2a. The reference genome required in the MDS use case is hg38, while the MM use case supports both: hg19 and hg38, but the one used for the project was hg19.

2b. The SCD use case proposes different references for imputation as TopMed or 1000Genomes

Other recommendations/Next steps:

3. Use of metadata standards:

An essential step to make FAIR is the standardized metadata, as it allows it findability and enhance reusability. In genomics, metadata provides context for its interpretation, it describes the sample and process from which these sequences or files were derived. To enhance the findability of the datasets, GenoMed4All metadata has been collected and will be available in the EOSC catalogue.

Besides, the use of standardized gene nomenclature is crucial for unambiguous and consistent gene reference. Studies on Human genes often follow the HUGO Gene Nomenclature Committee (HGNC) guidelines. In Genomed4all only the MDS use case, represent genes names in the final output file. Other relevant consideration would be the use of coordinates for SNPs (instead of rsID), since not all variants have rsID, it is not unequivocal and doesn't mention the specific nucleotide change.

4. Public Repositories:

For human genomic data sharing and reuse, various public repositories (EGA, dbGap or JGA) permanently archive and freely distribute data. For example, the European Genome-phenome Archive (EGA), facilitates the findability and reusability of the human genomic data generated in biomedical research projects and healthcare systems. Data is available to bona fide researchers only once data owners grant access to their data. Also point out the importance of sharing the bioinformatic pipelines and workflows publicly to enhance reproducibly. Several repositories exist for that purpose, for example: GitHub, bio.tools, SciCrunch.org or workflowhub.eu.

7 References

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